

FEASIBILITY TRIAL OF AN INTERVENTION TO IMPROVE ATTENDANCE AT DIABETIC RETINOPATHY SCREENING

TOPIC GUIDE (STAFF)

- Thank participant, introduce researcher & study
- Outline information sheet, consent form, highlight permission to record interview
- Remind and emphasise that it is a feasibility study i.e., we want to know how to improve the intervention and the study process, what to scope out how it works in real life practice – mention about possible full-scale trial - please be honest

Topic	Prompt/probe directly prompt
<p>Introduction Tell me what you know about the intervention and what your involvement was? How did it go?</p> <p>What did you think about the intervention at the start of the study? [mention initial visit] How does the intervention compare with what is usually done at the practice?</p>	<p>What parts are extra? What parts were done already?</p>
<p>Delivering the intervention Tell me about the audit; how did that work in this practice?</p> <p>Tell me about the last patient you reminded in person or over the phone; how did that go?</p> <p>How did your patients respond when you... <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reminded them during consultation? - Rang them? </p> <p>Tell me about sending out the letters & leaflet; how did that work?</p> <p>Thinking about the intervention overall; what worked well /less well? If you were doing it again what would you do differently?</p>	<p>Who did this? Why you/them? When did you do the audit?</p> <p>Why you/them? How long did it take? Did patients ask you about other things? What did you tell them? When did you do this? (i.e., between patients, during consultations, after hours)</p> <p>Positively or negatively?</p> <p>What would make it easier to deliver? Were there any parts you couldn't do? [remind them] Did you have to change anything?</p> <p>Were there any logistical issues? Use specific prompts here (resources, time, computer/software skills)</p>
<p>Influence What effect do you think the intervention had on patients? (What parts worked?) How do you think that change came about?</p> <p>Would you do anything differently now in terms of patients who have not attended retinopathy screening? What would you do different?</p>	<p>Why do you think that? (e.g. reminders, leaflet) What was it about them? (i.e. you, messages)</p> <p>Why? (e.g. motivation, new resource and knowledge, skills in audit)</p>

<p>What parts will you keep doing? Why?</p> <p>What part of the intervention was useful for delivery?</p> <p>How do you feel about the intervention now? (worthwhile?)</p> <p>[Mention full scale trial] Would you recommend the intervention to a colleague?</p>	<p>(i.e., the briefing/training, manuals, audit, prompts to remind patients, the script)? (more/different information? Paper-based vs. other?)</p> <p>Why? Is there anything which you would add to/change about the intervention? What did you think was good about it?</p> <p>Why/Why not?</p>
<p>How did you find the research process? How would you improve it?</p>	<p>What did you think of... practice visits, ongoing follow up calls, completing survey? Why do you say that?</p>
<p>To finish Will you continue the intervention? Is the intervention sustainable?</p> <p>[Mention full scale trial] How would you feel about other practices being involved?</p> <p>[Ask staff] Thinking back to when you first started the study, how did you find out about the study and your role in it? How did you feel about that?</p> <p>Why did the practice decide to take part in the study?</p> <p>Anything else you want to mention about your experience of delivering the intervention?</p>	<p>If yes; how will you continue / what will that look like? Why/Why not? (competing priorities, training, resources, funding, systems, culture, staff, potential adaptation, able to stick to it) What else could be done (alternatives)?</p> <p>Confident/concerned? Why?</p> <p>Positively or negatively? Did you have questions? How much support did you need?</p> <p>(e.g. payment, role, consequences, knowledge of uptake)</p>